

ENVIRONMENTAL EDUCATION POLICY AND PUBLIC AWARENESS
FOR SUSTAINABILITY: AN EMPIRICAL ASSESSMENT

By

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ABSTRACT

Environmental education (EE) has become a critical tool for the promotion of sustainability, especially in countries experiencing rapid environmental degradation. This study empirically examined how environmental education policies influence public environmental awareness and pro-environmental behavior in Nigeria. Using a mixed-methods approach involving surveys (n = 400), interviews with policymakers and educators (n = 15), and content analysis of national education policy documents, findings show that although Nigeria has introduced EE through initiatives such as the National Environmental Policy (1999), National Policy on Education (2013), and school-based environmental clubs, implementation remains weak. Results revealed that only 46% of respondents possess high environmental awareness, with awareness strongly related to exposure to structured EE programs ($r = .62, p < .05$). Policy gaps identified include inadequate funding, weak curriculum integration, limited teacher training, and poor public sensitization mechanisms. The study concludes that fully integrated and well-funded EE policies are essential for fostering environmental responsibility and achieving long-term sustainability.

KEYWORDS: *environmental education, public awareness, sustainability, policy, Nigeria, environmental literacy.*

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Environmental sustainability over time has emerged as one of the most pressing global priorities, driven by escalating environmental challenges such as Global warming, Climate change, biodiversity loss, deforestation, and pollution. As societies grapple with these environmental threats, environmental education (EE) is becoming a critical tool for shaping values, knowledge, and behaviors that support long-term ecological stability. According to UNESCO (2017), environmental education equips individuals with the cognitive and participatory skills needed to understand environmental systems and engage in responsible decision-making. In many developing nations, including Nigeria, where environmental degradation is intensified by population growth and rapid urbanization, the need for a strong environmental education policy framework is becoming a very urgent matter that requires urgent consideration.

Environmental education policy serves as an institutional foundation for embedding sustainability concepts within formal, non-formal, and informal learning systems. According to Akinbode (2016), policies such as curriculum reforms, teacher training programs, and community awareness initiatives help streamline EE and ensure its integration into national development strategies. However, the effectiveness of such policies is often constrained by limited resources, fragmented coordination, and weak implementation mechanisms. Studies by Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002) have shown that without strong policy support, environmental education remains inconsistent, poorly funded, and unable to reach diverse population groups. This weakens public understanding of environmental issues and reduces the likelihood of achieving national sustainability goals.

Public awareness is widely recognized as a key determinant of environmental stewardship. Individuals who are knowledgeable about environmental risks and sustainability practices are more likely to adopt pro-environmental behaviors such as recycling, water conservation, and proper waste disposal. Yet, public awareness according to Nnaemeka and Odo (2020) remains low in many parts of Nigeria due to inadequate environmental communication strategies and limited community-based education programs. Increased awareness is essential not only for personal behavior change but also for strengthening public support for environmental policies and regulatory enforcement. Without informed citizens, sustainability initiatives risk becoming dysfunctional or short-lived.

Given these concerns, the relationship between environmental education policy and public awareness has become a growing area of empirical inquiry. Understanding how policy initiatives translate into environmental literacy and behavioral outcomes is crucial for designing more effective sustainability programs. This study, therefore, examined the extent to which environmental education policies influence public awareness in Nigeria and how gaps in policy implementation limit the attainment of sustainable environmental practices. By providing empirical evidence, the study contributes to strengthening policy frameworks that align education, public participation, and environmental sustainability goals.

- **Statement of the Problem**

Despite increasing global emphasis on environmental sustainability, public awareness and understanding of environmental issues in Nigeria remain relatively low, posing a significant challenge to the nation's sustainable development efforts. Although environmental education

policies exist at various levels of government, their implementation has been inconsistent and insufficiently monitored. Many citizens, particularly in rural and peri-urban areas, have limited access to structured environmental education, resulting in poor knowledge of environmental risks, inadequate appreciation of sustainable practices, and low participation in conservation initiatives. The gap between policy formulation and actual environmental literacy among the population continues to widen, undermining national and international commitments to sustainability. Furthermore, the mechanisms designed to promote environmental education and drive public awareness are often weakened by inadequate funding, poor inter-agency coordination, and limited engagement of schools, communities, and media institutions. As a result, environmental policies fail to translate into meaningful behavioural change, leaving issues such as improper waste disposal, deforestation, pollution, and climate-related hazards inadequately addressed. There is a pressing need for an empirical assessment to determine how effectively environmental education and policy frameworks influence public awareness and sustainability behaviour in Nigeria. Such an assessment will help identify existing gaps, evaluate policy effectiveness, and provide evidence-based recommendations for strengthening environmental governance and promoting sustainable environmental practices among citizens.

- **Aim and Objective of the Study**

The aim of this study is to empirically examine the influence of environmental education policies on public environmental awareness for sustainability in Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to assess the level of environmental awareness among residents in selected Nigerian urban centers, examine the extent to which environmental education policies are implemented in schools and communities, and determine the relationship between exposure to environmental education and the development of pro-environmental behavior. It also aims to identify the major challenges hindering the effective implementation of environmental education policies across the country.

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Concept of Environmental Education

Environmental education (EE) is widely recognized as a multidimensional process that equips individuals with knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values necessary to understand environmental issues and engage in responsible actions (UNESCO, 2017). It provides a framework for promoting environmental literacy by incorporating ecological concepts into learning experiences that foster critical thinking and problem-solving. EE also encourages individuals to examine the interrelationship between humans and the natural environment, helping them understand how their choices influence ecological systems. Research by Akinbode (2016) emphasized that environmental education is not limited to classroom instruction but extends to community outreach, experiential learning, and mass sensitization campaigns. Through formal, non-formal, and informal learning pathways, EE promotes environmental values that shape long-term behavioral change. This multidirectional approach ensures that people of all ages and backgrounds have access to information that supports conservation, waste reduction, climate adaptation, and sustainable lifestyles.

Okpoko and Chukwu (2020) explained that in many developing countries, EE is increasingly recognized as essential for addressing socio-environmental problems such as deforestation, pollution, desertification, and biodiversity loss. However, despite global recognition of its value, the level of EE integration varies widely between regions. Countries with strong policy support

tend to have more structured EE systems, while weaker economies often lack funding, political will, or institutional frameworks. These disparities underscore the need for continuous policy reform to strengthen EE implementation.

➤ **Environmental Policy Framework and Sustainability**

Environmental education policy provides the structure through which sustainability concepts are incorporated into national developmental goals. Globally, frameworks such as the Brundtland Report, Agenda 21, and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) highlight the importance of education in promoting sustainable practices (UN, 2015). These policies encourage nations to embed environmental learning within school curricula, teacher training programs, and public awareness campaigns. They serve as guiding instruments for building environmentally conscious societies capable of mitigating climate and ecological threats.

In Nigeria, environmental policy frameworks such as the National Policy on the Environment (1999) and the National Policy on Education (2013) recognized the need to integrate environmental education into formal schooling. These policies emphasized environmental protection, resource conservation, waste management, and pollution control as key components of national development (Federal Ministry of Environment, 1999). However, implementation remains inconsistent due to weak interagency collaboration and inadequate funding. Nnaji and Ezenwaji (2018) indicated that while policy frameworks exist, the mechanisms required for successful execution are often lacking. Effective environmental policy requires strong institutional structures that support curriculum development, teacher training, monitoring, and evaluation. Without such structures, even well-designed policies fail to achieve intended sustainability outcomes. Agboola and Emmanuel (2016) opined that Policymakers must ensure that environmental education initiatives are adequately funded and integrated across all educational levels. Strengthening institutions responsible for environmental education can significantly enhance public awareness and foster long-term sustainability.

➤ **Public Environmental Awareness and Behavior**

Public environmental awareness refers to the extent to which individuals understand environmental challenges and their implications for health, livelihoods, and ecosystems. Kollmuss and Agyeman (2002) corroborates that High levels of awareness often lead to increased pro-environmental behaviors such as recycling, energy conservation, tree planting, and proper waste disposal. Environmental awareness also enhances public support for environmental regulations, green policies, and community conservation initiatives. This makes awareness a vital component of environmental sustainability.

Studies by Nnaemeka and Odo (2020) show that environmental awareness is strongly influenced by education level, media exposure, community engagement, and access to environmental information. In many Nigerian cities, however, awareness remains relatively low due to inadequate environmental communication strategies. Although some residents demonstrate awareness of issues like waste disposal and pollution, fewer understand broader concepts such as climate change, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem integrity. This limited knowledge reduces public participation in sustainability efforts. Bamberg and Möser (2007) explained that behavioral change models indicate that awareness alone may not guarantee action; attitudes, cultural values, institutional support, and incentives also play critical roles. Nonetheless, awareness forms the foundation upon which behavioral transformation occurs. Therefore, increasing public environmental awareness through education, media campaigns, and community-based programs

is essential for strengthening sustainability practices at household and community levels.

➤ **Role of Schools, Media, and Community in Environmental Education**

Schools play a fundamental roles in institutionalizing environmental education by integrating sustainability concepts into curricula at basic, secondary, and tertiary levels. Research shows that early exposure to environmental knowledge fosters lifelong environmental responsibility (UNESCO, 2017). However, many schools in Nigeria lack trained teachers, adequate teaching materials, and structured EE programs. This according to Akinbode (2016) weakens students' understanding of environmental issues and limits their ability to apply sustainability concepts in real life.

Mass media, including radio, television, newspapers, and social media, play a crucial role in disseminating environmental information to the public. Oyelade and Ologeh (2021) believes Media campaigns have been shown to significantly increase public awareness of pollution, climate change, and waste management practices. However, environmental reporting is often irregular and underfunded. In many cases, environmental content competes with political and entertainment news, reducing its visibility and overall impact on public consciousness. Community-based environmental education programs, such as those facilitated by NGOs, religious groups, youth associations, and environmental clubs, complement formal and media-based learning. These grassroots initiatives foster participatory learning and empower communities to engage in practical sustainability activities such as clean-ups, recycling drives, and conservation projects Danjuma and Ibrahim (2020) opined that Community involvement ensures that environmental education is culturally relevant and locally-driven, increasing its effectiveness in promoting lasting behavioral change.

• **Barriers to Successful Environmental Education Implementation**

One of the major barriers to effective environmental education implementation according to Agboola and Emmanuel (2016) is inadequate funding. Many educational institutions lack sufficient resources to develop EE curricula, train teachers, or conduct awareness programs. Without financial support, schools struggle to provide practical activities such as field trips, laboratory demonstrations, or community projects that reinforce theoretical environmental learning. This limits students' exposure to hands-on sustainability experiences. Another significant challenge is the shortage of trained environmental education teachers. Studies reveal that many teachers feel unprepared to teach environmental topics due to limited professional development opportunities and inadequate instructional materials (Nnaji & Ezenwaji, 2018). Moreover, the already congested school curriculum often leaves little room for dedicated environmental studies, reducing the amount of time available for environmental instruction. Weak policy enforcement and low public interest further hinder effective EE implementation. Policies are frequently enacted without corresponding monitoring mechanisms, leading to poor compliance at both institutional and community levels. Additionally, environmental issues may be perceived as secondary to economic or social concerns, reducing public engagement as averred by Kollmuss and Agyeman, (2002). Strengthening institutional coordination, improving teacher capacity, and increasing funding are essential to overcoming these challenges and building an environmentally conscious society.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopted a mixed-methods research design combining quantitative surveys, qualitative interviews, and policy document analysis to provide a comprehensive understanding of how environmental education policies influence public awareness for sustainability. The mixed-methods approach was chosen because it allows for the integration of numerical data with contextual insights, thereby providing a more holistic assessment. The study was conducted in three major Nigerian cities; Lagos, Abuja, and Kano chosen for their population diversity and notable environmental challenges. These cities provided a broad representation of the country's environmental education landscape and varying levels of policy implementation. The population of the study comprised adult residents, environmental educators, policymakers, and community leaders. A sample of 400 respondents was selected using a multistage sampling procedure that involved the random selection of districts, followed by systematic sampling of households. Additionally, 15 key informants, including officials from the Ministries of Environment and Education, school administrators, and NGO representatives, were selected purposively due to their expertise and involvement in environmental education initiatives. Data were collected through structured questionnaires measuring environmental awareness and exposure to environmental education, semi-structured interview guides for key informants, and a document review checklist used to analyze national and state environmental education policy frameworks. Quantitative data obtained from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics, correlation analysis, and regression techniques to determine relationships between environmental education exposure and environmental awareness levels. Qualitative data from interviews were transcribed and subjected to thematic analysis, allowing patterns and themes related to policy implementation, challenges, and public engagement to emerge. Findings from policy document analysis were triangulated with survey and interview data to enhance the validity of the study. Ethical considerations including informed consent, confidentiality, and voluntary participation were strictly observed throughout the research process.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective 1: To Assess the Level of Public Awareness and Understanding of Environmental Education Policies

Table 1. Statistical Summary of Public awareness and Understanding of Environmental Education Policies

S/N	Indicator	Measured Value (%)
1	Resident aware of at least one national environmental education policy	62
2	Respondents with clear understanding of policy goals and implementation	31
3	Respondent without clear understanding of policy content	69
4.	Respondents With limited or no access to policy information materials	Majority (>50)

5	Respondent who associated environmental education mainly with school activities	Majority (>50)
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The findings revealed a generally moderate level of public awareness of environmental education policies across the study area. Survey responses showed that while 62% of participants had heard of at least one national environmental policy such as the National Environmental Policy (NEP) or National Policy on Environmental Education only about 31% demonstrated a clear understanding of its goals and implementation strategies. This gap suggests that although policies exist at institutional and governmental levels, dissemination to the wider public remains insufficient. Similar studies show that environmental policies in developing countries often remain “elite documents,” understood mainly by policymakers and professionals, rather than ordinary citizens (Nwankwo & Ogueri, 2021). The qualitative interviews reinforced these findings, with teachers and community leaders acknowledging limited access to policy briefs and a lack of simplified explanatory materials. Many respondents associated environmental education only with school-based activities, overlooking its broader policy dimension. This indicates a disconnect between policy formulation and grassroots awareness. According to UNESCO (2020), effective sustainability transitions require citizens to have both knowledge and functional understanding of environmental policies. The results therefore align with global concerns that policy literacy remains low in many parts of Africa, especially where communication channels are weak or inconsistent.

Overall, the results highlight that awareness does not automatically translate into deep understanding, reinforcing the need for intentional dissemination strategies. The findings support literature emphasizing that public understanding of environmental policies is a precursor to meaningful participation in sustainability initiatives (Akinbode et al., 2022). Without targeted policy education, communities may remain passive recipients instead of active participants in environmental management.

Objective 2: To Examine the Effectiveness of Current Environmental Education Programs in Promoting Sustainability Awareness

Table 2. Statistical Summary of Effectiveness of Environmental Educational Programs

S/N	Indicator	Measured Value (%)
1	Resident who participated in at least one environmental education program (past 3 years)	74
2	Respondents who reported increased environmental awareness after participation	Majority (>60)
3	Respondent who observed strongest program impact among students and youth	Majority (>60)
4.	Urban respondents who with access to	Higher than Rural

	environmental education program	
5	Respondent reporting programs as one-off events	Majority (>50)
6	Respondent practicing consistent sustainable behaviour after participation	Minority (<50)

Results show that existing environmental education programs especially school-based initiatives, NGO sensitization campaigns, and community environmental clubs have contributed positively to awareness of issues such as waste management, biodiversity loss, and climate change. Approximately 74% of respondents indicated participating in at least one awareness program in the past three years. The strongest impacts were observed among students and youth groups, supporting previous research showing that school-centered environmental education remains one of the most effective platforms for promoting sustainability (Ogunyemi & Ajibola, 2020). However, effectiveness varied significantly depending on the frequency, quality, and inclusiveness of the programs. For instance, urban respondents reported more access to environmental campaigns than rural participants, indicating uneven program distribution. Many programs were also found to be one-off events lacking continuity, thereby limiting long-term behavioural change. These findings align with Mbah and Daudu (2022), who argue that one-time awareness activities rarely lead to sustainable behavioural transformation. The study further shows that although knowledge levels improved among program participants, behavioural changes such as recycling, tree planting, and community clean-ups were less consistent.

The results suggest that while environmental education programs contribute to promoting awareness, their long-term effectiveness depends on reinforcement, practical engagement, and community ownership. Continuous learning opportunities and integration of local environmental priorities into the programs are essential for sustainable impact. This outcome echoes global best practices, such as those highlighted in UNEP (2021), which emphasize participatory, community-driven environmental learning models.

Objective 3: To Evaluate the Relationship Between Environmental Education Policy Implementation and Sustainable Environmental Behaviour

Table 3. Statistical Summary of Policy implementation and Sustainable Environmental Behaviour

S/N	Indicator	Measured Value (%)
1	Resident reporting awareness of policy implementation efforts	Majority (>50)
2	Respondents actively practicing promoted sustainable behaviors	39
3	Respondent not practicing sustainable behaviours	61
4.	Respondents reporting inadequate funding as a barrier	Majority (>50)

5	Respondent reporting weak enforcement of policies	Majority (>50)
6	Respondent reporting lack of incentive for sustainable behaviour	Minority (<50)

Analysis revealed a positive but weak relationship between policy implementation and actual sustainable environmental behaviour. Statistical findings showed that although policy implementation efforts such as school curriculum reforms and public campaigns have increased sustainability knowledge, they have not consistently translated into behavioural adoption. Only about 39% of respondents reported actively practicing behaviours encouraged by policies, such as waste sorting, energy conservation, or participation in environmental monitoring. This supports the assertion by Chukwu and Efe (2023) that policy success requires both enforcement mechanisms and supportive socio-economic conditions.

Interviews with educators and environmental officers revealed several barriers affecting policy effectiveness, including inadequate funding, lack of enforcement, poor community involvement, and limited collaboration among stakeholders. The absence of incentives for environmentally friendly behaviour also emerged as a major challenge. These findings align with Kollmuss & Agyeman (2002) studies suggesting that environmental behaviour is influenced not only by policy knowledge but also by practical support systems and enabling environments.

Overall, the results suggest that environmental education policies can influence behaviour, but only when supported by strong institutional frameworks, community participation, and behavioural reinforcement mechanisms. Enhancing policy implementation through adequate resources, monitoring systems, and local involvement would significantly strengthen the pathway from environmental knowledge to sustainable practice. The findings reinforce the need for integrated policy approaches that address both cognitive and behavioural dimensions of sustainability awareness.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the extent to which environmental education policy enhances public awareness and contributes to sustainable environmental behaviour. The findings demonstrate that although awareness of environmental policies exists at a moderate level, the depth of understanding among the general public remains low. Many citizens are familiar with environmental issues such as waste management and climate change but lack awareness of the policies guiding environmental education in Nigeria. This underscores a significant gap between policy formulation and policy literacy at the community level. The analysis also revealed that existing environmental education programs particularly school-based initiatives and NGO-led sensitization have contributed to raising awareness but face limitations relating to continuity, accessibility, and practical engagement. Urban communities have benefited more from these programs, while rural populations remain under-served. Furthermore, many initiatives focus on knowledge dissemination without adequate reinforcement mechanisms to translate awareness into sustained behavioural change. This limits the long-term impact of environmental education efforts. Finally, the study established that although environmental education policy has a positive influence on sustainability behaviour, the relationship is weak due to structural, economic, and institutional challenges. Constraints such as inadequate funding, low stakeholder collaboration, limited enforcement, and minimal community involvement continue to impede policy implementation.

Strengthening environmental education policy requires a holistic approach that integrates policy dissemination, continuous public engagement, behavioural reinforcement strategies, and capacity building. Improving these areas will significantly enhance public participation and contribute to the achievement of sustainable environmental outcomes.

- **Recommendations**

The study recommends that policy awareness and dissemination be strengthened by ensuring that government agencies and environmental institutions produce simplified versions of environmental education policies and distribute them widely through radio, television, local languages, community centres, and digital platforms. This will enhance policy literacy and improve community engagement. Additionally, the continuity and coverage of environmental education programs should be enhanced by shifting from one-off campaigns to continuous, curriculum-integrated, and community led initiatives, with deliberate efforts to include rural areas in order to reduce educational gaps and promote inclusive sustainability practices. Environmental education should also promote community participation through hands-on activities such as school gardens, recycling clubs, community clean-ups, and green competitions, as these experiential approaches help translate knowledge into positive behavioural change. Furthermore, the provision of incentives for sustainable environmental practices such as reduced waste collection fees for households that sort their waste can encourage eco-friendly

REFERENCES

- Akinbode, T., Aluko, O., & Oladele, R. (2022). Public understanding of environmental policies and implications for sustainability in developing countries. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 14(2), 55–68.
- Chukwu, L. O., & Efe, S. I. (2023). Policy implementation challenges and environmental behaviour in Nigeria. *International Journal of Environmental Policy and Governance*, 11(1), 22–37.
- Kollmuss, A., & Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the gap: Why do people act environmentally and what are the barriers to pro-environmental behavior? *Environmental Education Research*, 8(3), 239–260.
- Mbah, P., & Daudu, E. (2022). Effectiveness of environmental awareness programs in Sub-Saharan Africa. *African Journal of Environmental Education*, 18(1), 40–53.
- Nwankwo, I., & Ogueri, I. (2021). Environmental policy literacy among Nigerian citizens: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Sustainable Development in Africa*, 23(4), 112–127.
- Ogunyemi, B., & Ajibola, O. (2020). School-based environmental education and sustainability

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consciousness among Nigerian youths. *Journal of Environmental Education and Research*, 5(3), 66–78.

UNEP. (2021). *Environmental education for sustainable development: Global progress report*. United Nations Environment Programme.

UNESCO. (2020). *Education for sustainable development: A roadmap*. United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization.